

THERMOGRAPHIC EVALUATION OF CFRP SPECIMENS DRILLED WITH CONVENTIONAL AND ABRASIVE WATER JET TECHNIQUES

M. Saleem¹, L. Toubal², R. Zitoune³, H. Bougherara^{1*}

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Ryerson University, Toronto, Canada, ²Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Quebec at Trois-Rivieres, Trois-Rivieres, Canada,

³Institut Clement Ader (ICA), IUT-A of Toulouse university, Toulouse France

* Corresponding author (habiba.bougherara@ryerson.ca)

Keywords: *Conventional drilling, Waterjet, surface quality, Fatigue, Damage*

Abstract

The aim of this paper is to analyze the influence of the machining process on the mechanical behaviour of composite plates under cyclic loading. For this purpose, an experimental study using several carbon fibre-reinforced polymer composite plates drilled with conventional machining (CM) using a cutting tool and non-conventional machining that utilized abrasive water jet machining (AWJM) was carried out. During fatigue tests, damage evolution and thermal dissipation were measured, using an MTS 322 mechanical tester and an infrared camera. Fatigue testing results showed that damage accumulation in specimens drilled with the CM process was higher than the AWJM specimens. Moreover, the endurance limit for composite plates drilled with the non-conventional process was approximately 10% higher as compared to specimens drilled with the conventional machining technique. This difference could be related to the initial surface integrity after machining, induced by the difference in the mechanism of the material removal between the two processes. This was confirmed by scanning electron microscope (SEM) tests conducted after a destructive sectioning of the specimens before fatigue testing.

1 Introduction

Currently, composite materials are used within primary load carrying aircraft structures. Recent examples are the Boeing 787 and Airbus A350XWB in which the composite content has increased to 50–60% by weight. However, the joining of a composite element on a structure often requires the manufacturing of holes in order to place bolts or rivets. To obtain these holes, different machining

processes can be used including conventional machining and abrasive water jet machining. However, these machining processes can introduce various damages onto the structure such as delamination at the entry and exit of the hole, fibres pull-out, micro cracks and resin degradation [1, 2]. Such resulting damages can cause significant reduction in both the tensile and compressive strength of the composite structure. In the literature, only few studies are interested in identifying the influence of damages induced by the process of machining on mechanical behaviour [3-5]. Krishnaraj *et al.* [6] observed the effect of drilling parameters on the strength of a drilled hole in a composite material made of glass fibre reinforced plastic (GFRP). They noted that specimens drilled at higher feed rates failed at a lesser load than specimens drilled at lower feed rates [6]. This can be explained by the fact that high feed rate provoke a delamination at the hole, which in turn affects the failure load. In the work conducted by Zitoune *et al.* [7], it was shown that failure loads of specimens with conventional drilled holes are inferior to those with moulded holes. In addition, specimens with drilled holes represent brutal fractures and specimens with moulded holes have progressive fractures. Similarly, experimental tests conducted by Persson *et al.* [3] showed that failure stresses of specimens with drilled holes using an axial drilling process with a dagger drill (PCD) during a fatigue test were 29% less compared to specimens with drilled holes using an orbital machining process such as the KTH process. This difference in the failure stress can be related to the difference of the quality of the machined surface (i.e. wall of the holes). More precisely, with a dagger drill the fibres pull-out and thermal degradation located on the wall of the holes is more important compared to those

located on the wall of the holes when the machining is carried out using the orbital process. To avoid such problems, it is proposed to obtain holes through non-conventional machining like water jet techniques with the addition of abrasive materials. It is well known that a machined surface produced by AWJM is free from abnormalities like delamination and thermal or non-thermal stresses along the cutting path [8]. It is important to point out that the grit size and standoff distance are the most significant parameters affecting the surface finish in water jet techniques [9, 10]. With the abrasive water jet technique, the machined surface produced is almost without any heat affected zones or residual stress [11]. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to investigate the influence of the surface topology created by non-conventional machining (AWJM) and conventional machining using a twist drill, on the mechanical behaviour of the composite plates with a circular hole. To achieve this objective, damage evolution and endurance limit during fatigue testing were carried out.

2 Materials and methods

Unidirectional (UD) prepregs of 0.26 mm made of carbon/epoxy are used to manufacture carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) specimens. The raw material of laminated structures are provided by Hexcel composites and are referenced as UD HexPly T700-M21GC with 58% fibre content and 1.6% void content. The stacking sequence of the composite panels is $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$. Two sets of specimens were used in the current experiments: the first set of specimens was composed of five composite plates with AWJM holes having diameters of 6 mm, while the second set was composed of four plates with holes machined with a conventional drill bit. The dimensions of the specimens were 270 mm long, 45 mm wide and 2.1 mm thick. All holes were situated at the center of the plates. The machining of the holes were carried out on a numerically controlled machine. For the CM technique, carbide drills with two lips were used to machine the holes. The spindle speed and feed rate were respectively 2020 rpm and 0.1 mm/rev. Two abrasive sizes of 120 and 220 microns along with a waterjet pressure of 145 MPa were used for AWJM. The standoff distance of 4 mm and a waterjet incidence angle of 90° were kept constant during the drilling process. Note that

all of the drilled specimens were roughly identical from a mechanical properties viewpoint.

We intended to measure the fatigue at different maximum stress levels ranging from 17% to 65% of ultimate tensile strength (UTS). Therefore, tensile tests were performed on four samples following the ASTM D 3039 standard to determine the UTS. The tests were realized with an Instron electromechanical testing machine model 4206, equipped with a 150 kN load cell. The average value of the ultimate tensile strength was 205 MPa (17.35 kN) and the average total elongation was 9%. The tensile data did not show a difference in the ultimate failure strength between the four specimens.

In order to investigate the quality of the machined surface and its texture, a NANOVEA 400 series profilometer and SEM observation were used. For the surface roughness tests, a cut-off and transverse length of 1 and 2 mm respectively along the x and y-axis were used. The average surface roughness (Ra), maximum profile valley depth (Rv) and skewness (Rsk) were measured according to ISO 4287/1 standards using NANOVEA 3D software. A FLIR SC5000 infrared (IR) camera with a resolution of 320 x 240 and a temperature sensitivity less than 20 mK was used to monitor the specimen surface temperature (Fig. 1).

The fatigue tests were conducted at room temperature using an MTS 322 tester equipped with hydraulically operated wedge grips. An extensometer was used to monitor the local strain that allowed for the calculation of the stiffness degradation of the specimen during the cyclic loading. These axial tension-tension fatigue tests were conducted in a load control set up using a constant amplitude sinusoidal waveform, a loading frequency of 10 Hz and a stress ratio of 0.1 at various maximum applied stress levels. From the IR temperature plots it was possible to evaluate the damage evolution and the endurance limit of the specimens [12].

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Damage analysis

The change in stiffness during cyclic loading is commonly used to quantify the damage in the specimen. The damage accumulation (D) is related

to the change in the ratio of dynamic stiffness (E_d) to static stiffness (E_o) by the equation:

$$D = 1 - E_d/E_o \quad (1)$$

The damage profiles versus the normalized cycles (N/N_f , where $N_f=5000$ cycles) are shown in Figure 2. When conventional machining was used, the damage was less than 5% for loads below 8 kN (47% of UTS). When the load reached 9 kN (53% of UTS) the cumulative damage was around 10%. At 10 kN (59% of UTS) the specimens ruptured. For the specimens drilled with the abrasive water jet, the cumulative damage was about 10% for 9 kN load. The damage reached 30% at 10 kN and the specimens ruptured at 11 kN (65% of UTS).

This difference in the damage accumulation between conventional and non-conventional drilled specimens is mainly attributed to the machining process. This is supported by the surface topography (roughness) tests as shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that specimens machined by abrasive water jet were characterized by streak defects (Fig. 3a) in the same direction of the displacement of the jet and craters defect due to the impact of the abrasives on the fibres. Globally these damages were uniformly distributed on the wall of the hole. However, for specimens drilled with a conventional drill bit, surface roughness photographs (Fig. 3b) showed the presence of fibre pull-out areas and matrix degradation non-uniformly distributed. These pull-out areas are related to material removal mechanisms which are strongly influenced by the relative angle between the direction of the cutting speed and the direction of the fibres. In this case, the maximum damage due to fibres pull-out was observed when plies were oriented at -45° compared to the direction of the cutting speed. However, the minimum damage was located in the zone where the fibres formed an angle of $+45^\circ$ compared to the direction of the cutting speed. These observations are in good agreement with previous work conducted by Zitoune *et al.* [13] on the orthogonal cutting of UD composite specimens.

Although the average surface roughness was similar for both types of specimens ($S_a = 13.5 \mu\text{m}$ for AWJM and $S_a = 12.5 \mu\text{m}$ for CM), the fatigue behaviour for these specimens was different. One can conclude that unlike metallic materials, the criterion used for quantifying the quality of machining based on the average roughness (e.g., R_a , S_a , etc.) is not suitable for composite materials. Similar observations of the defects on hole's wall

are confirmed by SEM micrographs as shown in Figure 4.

At this stage of the current investigation, we tried to obtain a correlation between the thermographic analysis and the damage accumulation.

3.2 Damage and thermography

The deformation of a structure is usually followed by heat dissipation. When the material is deformed or is damaged, a part of the energy necessary to the starting and the propagation of the damage is irreversibly transformed into heat [12, 14-15]. Figure 5 presents the distribution of the surface temperature at 3, 8 and 11 kN for AWJM specimen.

For loads less than 7 kN, the temperature remained constant throughout the surface around the hole (Fig. 5a). For a load of 8 kN, temperature fluctuations increased but remained moderate (Fig. 5b). However, for a load of 11 kN, there was a significant increase in temperatures and the fluctuations in the area reached 100% (Fig.5c). This area was situated at $\pm 45^\circ$ from the axis of the load, which also represented the axis of the direction of the plies. A similar pattern was observed in the case of the specimens with conventional machining. However, temperature fluctuations in the CM specimens were significant for loads less than those machined with abrasive water jet.

Figure 6 depicts the evolution of the maximum temperature and damage before the final failure of the specimen. Two stages for the temperature evolution were distinguished. In the first stage, the variation of the temperature was due to the thermoelasticity of the material and the friction between layers (i.e., fibres/fibres and/or fibres/matrix), whereas in the second stage, the temperature reached a balance that was due to saturation in the damage. With the increase in the loading, the rate of the damage and the frictions become more important. This stability was followed by an abrupt increase of the damage and temperature of the specimen corresponding to the rupture [12, 14].

At this stage, the following question may rise:

Does the machining-related defects observed in Figures 3 and 4 influence the limit of endurance? To answer this question, further analysis is indeed needed.

3.3 Endurance Limit Analysis

In general, the endurance limit is obtained by Whöler curves (stress vs. cycles). This endurance limit can also be obtained from the temperature stabilization curves [15] by intersecting the two straight lines that interpolates the stabilization temperature ($\Delta T = (T_f - T_0)$) and the corresponding stress level. The profile of ΔT at 5000 cycles for different loads for CM and AWJM specimens is shown in Figure 7. As can be seen, the endurance limit of the specimen drilled using CM (Fig. 7a) was lower than that of AWJM (Fig. 7b). The values of the endurance limit for five conventional drilled specimens and five abrasive water jet specimens were 83.3 ± 4 MPa and 93.5 ± 0.76 MPa respectively. Based on the above analysis, we can advance that the type of defects generated by machining processes as shown in Figures 3 and 4 may be the cause of this variation in the endurance limit values of the composite specimens.

4 Damaged Surface Morphology

4.1 CM Specimen

CF/Epoxy fractured specimens were examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) for the fractographic characterization of the machined surface after specimen failure during fatigue step loading. CM specimens loaded in axial tension failed in various modes as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8-a illustrates the damage mechanism such as longitudinal and interface debonding/interlaminar shear, crack propagation due to the initial fibre pull-out and matrix degradation areas generated during the CM process as shown in the surface roughness and SEM images (Fig. 3 and Fig. 4) obtained before fatigue loading. These cracks were propagated due to the shear between the planes owing to the axial mechanical load in composite with stacking sequence of $[\pm 45^\circ]$.

The mechanically fatigued specimen also exhibited transverse fracture (Fig. 8-a) in matrix degradation areas resulting from the drilling hole in fibre's transverse direction. Figure 8-b showed loose fibres and delamination due to fibre pull-out and matrix degradation. These loose fibres subsequently reduced the strength of CM specimens. It is worth mentioning that the matrix degradation and fibre pull-out in CM specimens affected the fibre-matrix load transfer, consequently, that led to significant material degradation under tensile loading conditions. The different fracture modes generated

under fatigue cyclic load in the CM specimens led to reduction in various mechanical properties such as decrease in elastic modulus, increase in damage accumulation (Fig. 2) and decrease in the endurance limit (Fig. 7).

Hence, major observable damage, fibre pull-out and matrix degradation generated during CM acts as a stress concentrator for crack initiation and propagation at the edge of the hole and then gradually propagated width-wise toward the edge of the specimen, along the fibre direction i.e. 45° (Figure 5), subsequently leading to catastrophic failure of CM specimens. The final failure was not perpendicular to the tensile load, but is oriented parallel to the fibre direction (Fig. 5c).

4.2 AWJM Specimen

Post mortem surface observation of AWJM specimens after fatigue loading was conducted using a scanning electron microscope. Surface roughness and SEM images presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4 showed results before fatigue loading, whereas SEM images presented in Figure 9 showed streak marks in the direction of the water jet after fatigue loading. There was no visible fracture mode observed in these images (Fig. 9). However, internal failure in composite specimens is normally initiated before any macroscopic changes are observed. The final failure of the AWJM specimen occurred according to that two stages, explained in section 3.2.

5 Conclusion

This paper presents experimental results of mechanical behaviour during fatigue tests on composite specimens drilled with two different machining processes: conventional and abrasive water jet machining. The composite specimens used were made from CF/Epoxy UD prepregs. Based on this experimental analysis, the following conclusions were drawn:

- Both specimens have shown similar damage for loads less than 46% of UTS. For loads above this value, the damage is more significant for the specimens drilled using conventional machining.
- The maximum temperature profiles in the area surrounding the hole (i.e. examined area) follow the same evolution as the damage profiles for both machining processes. However, the presence of defects induced by the cutting tool

in conventional machining (fibres pull-out and the resin degradation) provokes more heat dissipation than ridges and crater defects observed on the walls of the holes machined by abrasive water jet (Fig.4).

- The endurance limit for specimens drilled with abrasive water jet is 10% more than the one drilled with conventional machining.

Fig. 1. Experimental setup for tension-tension fatigue testing with IR camera.

Fig. 2. Comparison of the evolution of the damage for various level of loading with (a) conventional machining and (b) abrasive water jet machining.

Fig. 3. Cartography of the surface roughness of the wall of the hole for different specimens, hole obtained with (a) abrasive water jet and (b) conventional machining using a cutting tool.

Fig. 4. SEM photographs comparing the hole surfaces machined with two different techniques. Circular hole machined with (a) abrasive water jet and (b) conventional cutting tool.

Fig. 5. Temperature maps of AWJM specimen for various loads (a) 3 kN, (b) 8 kN and (c) 11 kN.

Fig. 6. Comparison between the change of the maximum temperature and the damage for different level of loading : 5 kN, 7 kN and 9 kN.

Fig. 7. Graphical representation of the endurance limit for (a) CM and (b) AWJM specimens. The endurance limit is obtained by intersecting the two straight lines that interpolates the experimental data of the stress and temperature.

Fig. 8. SEM micrograph showing cross section of circular hole of CF/Epoxy composite, circular hole obtained with CM technique

Fig. 9 SEM micrograph showing cross section of circular hole of CF/Epoxy composite, circular hole obtained with AWJM technique

References

- [1] R. Zitoune and F. Collombet "Numerical prediction of the thrust force responsible of delamination during the drilling of the long-fibre composite structures". *Composites Part A*, Vol. 38, No. 3, pp 858–66, 2007.
- [2] W. Konig, C. Wulf, P. Grab and H. Willerscheid "Machining of fibre reinforced plastics". *CIRP Annals*, Vol. 34, No. 2, pp 537-547, 1985.
- [3] E. Persson, I. Eriksson and L. Zackrisson "Effects of hole machining defects on strength and fatigue life of composite laminates". *Composite Part A*, Vol. 28, pp 141–151, 1997.
- [4] D.D. Arola and M. Ramulu "Net-shape machining and the process dependent failure of failure of fibre-reinforced plastics under static loads". *Journal of composites and Technology and research, JCTRER*, Vol. 20, No. 4, pp 210-220, 1998.
- [5] P. Ghidossi, M. El Mansori and F. Pierron "Influence of specimen preparation by machining on the failure of polymer matrix off-axis tensile coupons". *Composite Science and Technology*, Vol. 66, pp 1857–1872, 2006.
- [6] V. Krishnaraj, S. Vijayarangan and A. Ramesh Kumar "Effect of drilling parameters on mechanical strength in drilling glass fibre reinforced plastic". *International Journal of Computer Applications in Technology*, Vol. 28, pp 87-93, 2007.
- [7] R. Zitoune, R. Crouzeix, F. Collombet, T. Tamine and Y. Grunevald "Behaviour of composite plates with drilled and moulded hole under tensile load". *Composite Structure*, Vol. 93, pp 2384-2391, 2011.
- [8] A.A. Abdel-Rahman "A Closed-form Expression for an abrasive waterjet cutting model for ceramic materials". *International Journal of Mathematical Models and Methods in Applied Sciences*, Vol. 5, pp 722-729, 2011.
- [9] P.H. Shipway, G. Fowler and I.R. Pashby "Characteristics of the surface of a titanium alloy following milling with abrasive waterjets". *Wear*, Vol. 258, pp 123-32, 2005.
- [10] M. Ramulu and D. Arola "The influence of abrasive waterjet cutting conditions on the surface quality of graphite/epoxy laminates". *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, Vol. 34, pp 295-313, 1994.
- [11] S. Y. Brooghani, H. Hassanzadeh and P. Kahhal "Modeling of single particle impact in abrasive water jet machining". *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology*, Vol. 36, pp 243-248, 2007.
- [12] L. Toubal, M. Karama and B. Lorrain "Damage evolution and infrared thermography in woven composite laminates under fatigue loading". *International Journal of Fatigue*, Vol. 28, pp 1867-1872, 2006.
- [13] R. Zitoune, F. Collombet, F. Lachaud, R. Piquet and P. Pasquet "Experiment-calculation comparison of the cutting conditions representative of the long fibre composite drilling phase", *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 65, pp 455-466, 2005.
- [14] B. Wei, S. Johnson and R. Haj-Ali "A stochastic fatigue damage method for composite materials based on Markov chains and infrared thermography". *International Journal of Fatigue*, Vol. 32, pp 350-360, 2010.
- [15] M.P. Luong "Fatigue limit evaluation of metals using an infrared thermographic technique". *Mechanics of Materials*, Vol. 28, pp 155–163, 1998.